

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DECISION TREE ALGORITHM IN DATA MINING

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Abstract. In this article we will discuss some Data Mining problems and their solution based on the Machine Learning algorithms. There are so many algorithms for using analyze and prediction. And we chose Decision Tree for beginning because of it is easier than others to understand and implementation. You can see the advantages and disadvantages of Decision tree, some Data Mining terminologies with definition and examples. Moreover, this article informs fundamental knowledge for beginners about what is Data Mining, where is it used and so on.

Keywords: Decision tree, Root node, Leaf node, sub-nodes, training data, entropy, Gini index, Information gain.

Introduction

Data Mining is the process of using a computer program to find relationships (mathematically) in data. It is considered that intellectual analysis of data is widely used today to solve various problems in various fields. The fields of application of Data Mining are used in the fields of analysis of specific tasks, interaction between people and technology, and things that people do not have time for. Nowadays, Data Mining is used in all human activities such as medicine, biology, genetics, applied researches and so on. Moreover, we have to tell about volume of data in the world. As you know, there are so much useless data to use by researcher in the areas. That is why, data collection and data preparation are fields considered in Data Mining (DM). Data Mining might help to solve two types of problems, classification and clustering. In order to determine relationships among data, Machine Learning algorithms are used by researchers and experts [1]. In this article, we will discuss some algorithms which are used in Data Mining. Before the discussion, need to define some terminologies of DM.

Training data – a set of training examples that we have to give the machine to learn something. It has to be already classified. Example: to determine whether a customer is likely to buy a laptop in the next year (Yes/No).

Table 1.

Training dataset.

Id	Gender	Age	Student?	Credit rating	Buy or not?
26	male	16	no	good	yes
42	female	59	no	excellent	yes
335	female	21	yes	fair	no
158	male	32	yes	fair	yes

Each row in the training data is known as an *instance*. You can see them in the table above as “Gender”, “Age”, and etc.

Each column is referred to as an *attribute* (*Id:26*, *Id:158*). And the *attributes* can be divided into two types:

- Output attribute – the one we want to predict;
- Input attributes – everything except output attributes.

According to the value of the attributes, there are two types of them: Nominal and Numeric. Nominal attributes have values that are “names” of categories (Male, Female, Yes/No in table above). Numeric attributes have values that are numbers and it makes sense to compare their values using “<” and “>” (age<24).

Decision Tree algorithm.

Decision Tree is a Supervised learning technique that we can use in Data Mining problems to solve such as both classification and regression problems. Mostly it is popular in use to classify object in dataset by experts. In a tree-structured classifier, where internal nodes illustrate the features of a dataset, branches represent the decision rules and each leaf node represents the result. We use two types of nodes in Decision tree algorithm: Decision node, Leaf node. Decision nodes are used to make any decision and have multiple branches, whereas Leaf nodes are the output of those decisions and do not contain any further branches [2]. As we know, tree is a type of graph in data structure, that is why this algorithm visual view is the same binary tree. A decision tree simply asks a question, and based on the answer (Yes/No), it further split the tree into subtrees.

Figure 1. Simple solution of classification problem above through Decision tree.

Definitely, for solving problem there are several steps to do. First step includes finding the Root Node and other Decision Nodes among input attributes. It is considered the main issue while implementing Decision Tree[3]. It is called Attribute Selection Measure (ASM). There are two types of technique for ASM:

- Information gain;
- Gini index.

Information Gain (IG). We can define information gain as a measure of how much information a feature provides about a class. Information gain helps to determine the order of attributes in the nodes of a decision tree.

$$Gain(S, A) = entropy(S) - \sum_{v \in Values(A)} \frac{|S_v|}{|S|} entropy(S_v)$$

Where,

S – total number of samples, S_v - subset of S, A – attribute A.

$$entropy(S) = -p_{\oplus} \log_2 p_{\oplus} - p_{\ominus} \log_2 p_{\ominus}$$

Where,

S is a collection of training examples, p_{+} the proportion of positive examples in S,

p_{-} the proportion of negative examples in S.

Calculation IG according to the training dataset above:

$$entropy[3+, 1-] = -\frac{3}{4} \log_2 0.75 - \frac{1}{4} \log_2 0.25 = 0.75 * 0.415 + 0.5 = 0.811$$

Entropy is in [0,1] interval. If either p_{+} or p_{-} equals to 0, then Entropy's value also equals to 0 (exception).

Then,

$$Values(Student?) = no, yes$$

$$S = [3+, 1-]$$

$$S_{yes} \rightarrow [1+, 1-]$$

$$S_{no} \rightarrow [2+, 0-]$$

$$IG(S, Student?) = entropy(S) - \frac{2}{4} * entropy(S_{yes}) - \frac{2}{4} * entropy(S_{no}) = 0.811 - \frac{2}{4} * 1 - \frac{2}{4} * 0 = 0.31 \blacktriangle$$

Gini index is a measure of impurity or purity used while creating a decision tree in the CART(Classification and Regression Tree) algorithm. It is absolutely opposite of Information gain, because low Gini index should be preferred than high Gini index in DT [3].

Gini index can be calculated using the below formula:

$$I_G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^s p_i^2$$

This index value is also determined in [0,1] interval.

In conclusion, Decision Tree algorithm has been used so many fields to predict and analyze data in AI history so far. Of course, there are various disadvantages to use some complicated problems in it, but still beneficial and simple algorithm to understand for AI and BI experts [5].

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